

METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH TO TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF INFORMATICS AT SCHOOLS

Sherboboev Kh.

Teacher at Karshi branch of Tashkent university of information technologies

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13122228>

Abstract. *The state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of education is based on the principles of the priority of universal values, human rights, the humanistic nature of education, the guarantee of everyone's constitutional rights to education, equal access to education [1]. The following are defined as the priority areas of education development: guaranteeing the rights, freedoms and legal interests of citizens in the field of education; equality in education, including the creation of conditions for persons with special psychophysical characteristics in their development, in accordance with their health and cognitive abilities, at all levels of basic education and additional education; creating the necessary conditions to meet the educational needs of a person, as well as the needs of society and the state in the formation of a person, training of qualified personnel.*

Keywords: *competency-based approach, operational-technological components, ideology, framework of formal and informal education.*

The main idea of the competency-based approach is that the definition of the content of education should not be limited to the definition of a certain amount of knowledge and skills acquired by students in the formal school education system. The practical aspect of education should be taken into account in terms of the following: the knowledge acquired in the formal school education system must be integrated with wider knowledge in order to be truly effective. In addition to the content of formal education, it is appropriate to include competences related to everyday activities, politics, culture, environmental protection, health care, etc. among the other competencies.

More precisely, the concept of competence can be given as follows:

- competence embodies the intellectual and skill components of education;
- the concept of competence includes not only cognitive and operational-technological components, but also motivational, moral, social and behavioral; it includes learning outcomes (knowledge and skills), a system of value orientations, etc.;
- competence means the ability to mobilize acquired knowledge, skills, experience and methods of self-development in a specific situation, in a specific activity;
- the concept of competence includes the ideology of interpreting the formed educational content;
- competence is formed not only in school, but also under the influence of the environment, that is, in the educational process within the framework of formal and informal education.

In accordance with this approach, the general education system should be focused on the formation of necessary competencies. Competence can be considered necessary if it has the following characteristics:

- has an integrative nature, that is, it incorporates a number of the same or closely related skills and knowledge related to wide areas of culture and activity (information, legal, etc.);
- multifunctional, that is, its mastery allows solving various problems in everyday life;
- applicable in different situations and interdisciplinary;
- requires significant intellectual development;
- multidimensional, that is, it includes different mental processes and intellectual abilities

It is important that all competencies require different types of actions (and, in addition, can be manifested only in certain situations):

alternative and reflex action;
interactive use of various tools;
entering and working in socially heterogeneous groups.

The analysis of these provisions shows that the concept of "educational competence" is deeper than the traditional interpretation of the term "competence". Thus, the dictionary of foreign words [2] interprets competence as "having knowledge, skills, abilities of a certain person", and competence as "having knowledge that allows one to judge something".

The strategy of implementing a competency-based approach is that each educational subject must first of all "work" to form the necessary competencies, to transform them into a form close to the course characteristics.

Required competencies include, for example:

- competence in the field of independent cognitive activity based on the acquisition of methods of learning from various sources of information, including those outside the classroom;
- competence in the field of civic and social activity;
- competence in the field of social and labor activity;
- competence in the household sphere;
- competence in social, cultural and recreational activities [3].

A key outcome of the education modernization strategy is the willingness and ability of school leavers to take personal responsibility for their own well-being and the well-being of society.

A.L.Semenov defines information competence as one of the priorities of general secondary education, and communicative competence as one of the types of information competence[4]. According to the reasonable opinion of the author, "Informatics and information technologies" is the basis of formation of information competence of the educational direction [5].

Information competence is considered as a new literacy, which primarily includes the skills of "active, independent processing of information by a person, making fundamentally new decisions in non-standard situations using technological tools", as well as "computer technical skills". It also includes "skills related to oral presentation, using an encyclopedia and large library, writing a personal letter, perceiving television advertising, and memorizing facts meaningfully" [6].

In conclusion, this can be achieved by distinguishing the types of activities characteristic of a competent approach. The description of this activity makes it possible to distinguish a certain system of concepts, the completeness of which is determined, first of all, by the correct choice of the type of activity. This competent approach requires an in-depth analysis of the current state of school education.

1. REFERENCES

2. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг “Таълим тўғрисида”ги қонуни 2020 йил 23 сентябрдаги 637-сонли. <https://lex.uz/docs/5013007>.
3. Катасонов В. Н. Философские предпосылки новоевропейской математики. Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени доктора философских наук. — М., 1995.
4. Turaev S.J. Determining physics value through methods of Gauss using software language Borland Delphi7. //Eastern European Scientific Journal. ISSN 2199-7977. DOI 10.12851/EESJ201805. – Ausgabe 3-2018. P. 424-429. (13.00.00; № 1).
5. Родился в 1950 году в семье инженеров — Льва Афанасьевича Семенова и Евгении Тихоновны Семеновой. Окончил московскую школу № 7 с углублённым изучением математики и информатики. 1972 г
6. Тураев С.Ж. Физика фанини ўқитишда C++ дастурлаш тили ва Microsoft Excel дастури имкониятларининг қиёсий таҳлили. //Таълим, фан ва инновациялар. Маънавий-маърифий, илмий-услубий журнал. № 3.— Тошкент, 2018. Б. 40-44. (13.00.00; № 18).
7. Тураев С.Ж., Одилов Ё.Ж. Маълумотлар базасини шакллантириш орқали графиклар ҳосил қилишда Borland Delphi7 дастурлаш тилидан фойдаланиш. // “Олий таълим муассасаларида фанларни ўқитишда замонавий педагогик ва ахборот технологияларидан фойдаланишнинг долзарб муаммолари” Республика илмий-амалий анжумани. – ҚДУ: Қарши, 2017.Б 239-241.